

EDITORIAL

JNANADEEPA
PJRSS ISSN 0972-33315
22/2, July-Dec. 2018, 5-8

Christian Leadership

The nine articles of this issue of Jnanadeepa focus on Christian leadership. The various dimensions of a Christian leader would necessarily be different from those trained with purely secular understandings. Some dimensions include acts of stewardship (leadership) servant leadership roles, the importance of values or character strengths, kingdom-oriented action and discipleship. These dimensions of a Christian leader arise at points of interaction between faith and secularism. Leaders have different personalities and styles of functioning and therefore operationalize their decisions in different ways. They develop their organizations or institutions according to their perspectives. Therefore, for a Christian leader, models and theories need to be developed that address leadership in Christian ways to influence the functioning of all leaders in today's world. Christian leadership draws from secular leadership theories and their interaction with understandings of leadership drawn from scripture and theology.

The ministries or works of Christian leaders can be just about anything in the reign of God. Works or ministries involve care of the flock or those whom the leader works with. Christian leaders are involved in teaching (instruction and education), preaching (discussion with follow-up) and healing (bringing to wholeness or building up) ministries (works), just like what Jesus did. Therefore, planning in keeping with the times is needed in these works. The

choice and continuation of ministries means that those involved in leadership roles should necessarily discern according to Christian principles. Discernment is paramount in any process of planning and decision making. It means a fair amount of skill development and application based on Christian principles. Also, it is expected that leaders develop skills and that they have a desire for their personal growth, in keeping with the times.

The focus of any leader or leadership role is the development of the ministries (works) globally and locally. Also, the leader should look for the growth of the various ministries in the institution/s. Ultimately a Christian leader who looks at the Church in today's fast developing world will need to have shifting styles, discernment, and apostolic planning, for an effective ministry.

The writers in this issue look at various aspects of Christian leadership in today's fast paced world. A reflection on "Shifting Leadership Style in The Church" by Bp.(Dr.) Percival Fernandez begins the issue. The lead article is by Dr. Ruth D'Souza, that address the issue of "The Christian Leader: Servant and Steward." She dwells on how Christian leadership as modelled by Jesus Christ is presented as an alternative to secular leadership. She articulates that Christian leadership begins with a premise that the Christian leader should develop a servant's heart. Her article explores the twin dimensions of servant leadership and steward leadership where the servant leader focuses on the well-being of the people being led, while the steward leader focuses on accomplishing the purpose of the owner. Dr. Ruth's article leads to the articles by Dr. Joseph Lobo SJ and Dr. Yesu Karunanidhi.

Dr. Joseph Lobo SJ, writes on "Prophetic Leadership: One Among Many Roles or A Model for All Roles?" and Dr. Yesu Karunanidhi writes on "Crisis - Conflict - Stress Management: Leadership Lessons from The Parable of a Father and Two Sons in Luke 15:11-32." In his article Dr. Joseph Lobo writes about prophetic leadership being one among the various leadership roles, and a possible model or perspective to shape all leadership roles. A prophetic leader is critical and creative and responds to the signs of the times. This happens to the leader in the light of the experience of God's continuing involvement in personal and

communitarian history. Prophetic leadership can establish fruitful interreligious bonds geared towards a shared mission of facilitating God's redemptive activity in the here and now.

Dr. Yesu Karunanidhi furthers this understanding through his analysis of leadership through the parable of the father and the two sons. The parable in Luke 15:11-32 reveals how the characters presented there instead of 'resolving' the crisis, conflict, and stress, 'manage' them by anchoring themselves not on persons or processes but on principles. The interplay of crisis-conflict-stress is studied, and managerial lessons are drawn for the Christian leaders today. This is followed by the article by Dr. Konrad Noronha SJ, which dwells on "Jesus' Charismatic Leadership." Jesus' exhibited charisma akin to the stars of today. The difference was that for Jesus, his charisma was not a personal objective, rather he was doing his Father's will. Jesus' mission involved his clashing with the bureaucracy of his time. He created a bond with his followers and his followers today can say that he has dominion over heaven and earth and of things seen and unseen.

Dr. Jose Parapully SDB throws light on the "Personality Dimensions of Church Leaders" in which he discusses characteristics required of Church Leaders. The article focuses on the personality dimensions of priests. It gives some understanding of personality and personality styles in psychology and moves on to describe characteristics of healthy and unhealthy personality. The article presents an analysis of personality profiles of priests in relation to characteristics as found in psychological theory and available research data. The article concludes with suggestions for priestly formation to enhance the healthy personality dimensions of Church leaders.

Dr. Jill Snodgrass, reflects on how leaders can "Engage God's Gift of Time," where time is often viewed as a commodity. God gifts us with time and we discern—wisely or not—how to engage it. Her article explores how conceptions of time are culturally constructed. She examines theological and scriptural perspectives on time, to posit a practical theology for how Christian leaders can receive the gift of time given by God and discern how to engage time as God intends.

The issue concludes with an article by Sherel Jeevan Mendonsa SJ where he writes on the important issue of “The Significance of Self-Awareness for Christian Leadership.” The article dwells on the significance of self-awareness for Christian leadership and reflects on self-awareness from philosophical and religious viewpoints. It concretely discusses the importance of self-awareness in some circles of Western philosophy, and through the concept of self-awareness in Buddhism. It further reflects on the importance accorded to self-awareness in contemporary corporate circles where self-awareness is now considered a critical leadership skill.

It is hoped that these articles will give Christian leaders ideas about how to be different. In the fast-moving world of today, utilizing the principles and practices derived from the teachings of Jesus, could help those in power work better with those who work with them. The principles of Jesus who is the leader par excellence, have stood the test of time.

Dr. Konrad Noronha SJ

Guest Editor

We are grateful to the Guest Editor, Dr Konrad Noronha SJ, Director and Coordinator, Pastoral Management Programme, JDV, for collecting the articles and editing this issue of the journal. Please note that the last two articles are additions by the Editor.

We are also happy to announce some formatting changes, which we hope will make the reading easier. Feedback will be appreciated!

We regret to announce the demise of Rev Dr Kurien Kunnumpuram SJ (1931-2018), the founder of this journal, on October 23, 2018. His obituary will be published in the next issue. -The Editor